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PERMEABILITY EVALUATION IN VACUUM-ASSISTED RESIN TRANSFER MOLDING OF CARBON FIBER REINFORCED PLASTICS

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#ICCM22

BACKGROUND

- Vacuum-assisted Resin Transfer Molding; VaRTM

Low Cost, Freedom in Design ○

Mechanical Properties Δ (Occurrence of Void and Dry Spot)

Optimize of Molding Condition by Flow Simulation

- Permeability

Defined in Darcy's Law, Flowability of Matrix Resin, Input Parameter for Flow Simulation

Problem Experimental Scatter **Large**, BENCHMARK **×**

Factors of Scatter

① Race-tracking;

Fluid's Flow between Preform and Mold

② Nesting; Phase Shift of Fabric Weave

Difference in **Gap between Fiber Yarns**, **Thickness**

Purpose

Examination of Permeability Measurements for Reducing Error

EXPERIMENTAL PROCEDURE

Material

Plain Woven Carbon Fiber Fabric

CK6261C, Toray, Number of Fibers: 12K
400 mm × 100 mm, 0° direction, 4 plies

2 Pack Type Epoxy Resin

XNR6815/XNH6815, Nagase Chemtex
Mixing Weight Ratio 100:30

Fabric Preparation

1. Using Glue for Restriction of Fabric Deformation
2. Pulling out 0° Fiber Yarns at Both Ends
3. Weave Shift as Nesting

VaRTM Equipment (Simultaneous)

Cancel the Difference of Epoxy Resin Condition

RESULTS and DISCUSSION

● Shape of Flow Front

Nearly Parallel to Weft Fiber Yarn

↳ Range of Race-tracking; Restricted

↳ Effect of Race-tracking to Permeability **REDUCE**

● Measured Permeability

In Simultaneous Measurement; Not coincide

↳ Difference in Microstructure of Preforms

Experimental Scatter [2 plies] < [4, 8 plies]

Mainly Distributed in **$0.6-0.7 \times 10^{-11} \text{ m}^2$**

CONCLUSION

Purpose

- © Single and Simultaneous Measurements of Permeability for Reduction in Experimental scatter
with Fabric Preparation and Materials Arrangement

Results

Flow Front Shape; Parallel to Weft Fiber Yarns

Permeability Values in Simultaneous Measurements; Not Coincident

Most of obtained permeability were distributed in the range of $0.6-0.7 \times 10^{-11} \text{ m}^2$.

Thank you for your kind attention